

Public Libraries and ICT Integration: A Dual Approach to Advancing SDG Goal 16 in North-Central Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose: Building on Sustainable Development Goal 16, this study examines how public libraries can utilise information and communication technology (ICT) to promote justice and peace. Research indicates that ICT improves public awareness, disseminates relevant information, optimises resource use, enhances service quality, and provides access to vital justice and peace information. Public libraries also play a crucial role in fostering social change, safeguarding fundamental liberties, and encouraging inclusive access to knowledge through digital resources and advocacy efforts.

Methodology: the descriptive survey design was chosen to investigate the relationship between public library ICT use and the implementation of SDG 16 in North-Central Nigeria. Using structured questionnaires, this design supports data collection from a large population, enabling respondents to express their opinions openly.

Findings: The findings emphasise the need for stronger regulation and funding of public libraries' ICT infrastructure to increase their impact on sustainable development. Public libraries must leverage ICT to enable effective information sharing and promote public engagement in justice and peace initiatives, the study finds.

Recommendations: The study recommends greater government and community support for ICT-based library initiatives and the implementation of strategic policies to enhance libraries' roles in promoting peace, justice, and resilient institutions.

Keywords: ICT, public libraries, peace and justice, SDG 16, information dissemination, sustainable development

Introduction

Libraries in low- and middle-income countries face challenges in cybersecurity readiness due to gaps in policy, technology, and workforce capacity. Without clear cybersecurity policies,

many libraries struggle to establish essential protocols, such as data classification and incident response (Hamidi & Singh, 2024). Weak national data protection laws and fragmented implementation of ICT or privacy frameworks leave libraries exposed to digital threats. Alenezi (2024) highlights the prevalence of outdated systems, unsecured networks, and missing firewalls, which make libraries highly vulnerable to malware, phishing, and data breaches. This combination of technological and regulatory shortcomings reduces institutional resilience and weakens basic cyber hygiene. Human factors worsen cybersecurity vulnerabilities in library systems. Akor et al. (2024) note that most library staff in under-resourced regions lack training in essential cybersecurity areas, such as encryption, digital forensics, and threat response, leaving them vulnerable to sophisticated attacks like phishing and ransomware. Without structured training programmes, staff and patrons become the weakest links in the cybersecurity defences. Routine tasks, such as failing to update antivirus software or opening malicious links, often expose systems to avoidable breaches. Many library staff, many of whom lack ICT backgrounds, are often assigned cybersecurity duties due to the shortage of trained technical personnel. Sabillon et al. (2019) propose an integrated strategy that localises national cybersecurity frameworks, increases infrastructure investment, and embeds ongoing professional development as a key institutional priority. Such systemic reforms are crucial for enhancing digital security in libraries, especially during the initial stages of technological transformation.

The implications of these challenges are especially significant when viewed within the broader context of the developmental goals of institutions like public libraries. Balôck (2020) argues that efforts to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 16, which promotes peace, justice, and strong institutions, are still hindered in North-Central Nigeria by intercommunal conflict, limited legal access, and weak governance structures. Public libraries are uniquely positioned to bridge these gaps by providing access to legal information, civic education, and platforms for engagement. However, as Alex-Nmecha and Igbinovia (2020) report, their contributions are often under-recognised due to insufficient funding, limited use of ICT, and a general lack of strategic focus. Although ICT offers significant potential for improving legal and governance-related services, Nwankwo et al. (2020) highlight that infrastructural and technological deficiencies prevent libraries from deploying digital legal repositories, virtual civic tools, or online dispute resolution systems. The lack of empirical data on how libraries use ICT for SDG 16 further hampers progress (Umar et al., 2021). Therefore, this study explores how public libraries in North-Central Nigeria can leverage ICT to support peacebuilding, legal empowerment, and institutional development. By identifying key challenges and practical opportunities, it aims to contribute both practical and scholarly insights to inform policy reforms, funding strategies, and ICT integration efforts in the regional library sector.

Literature Review

This study is based on the Knowledge Gap Theory, introduced by Tichenor, Donohue, and Olien in 1970, which argues that disparities in access to information significantly influence differences in civic engagement, legal awareness, and social participation. According to this theory, individuals with greater access to information are more likely to participate in governance and legal decision-making. Conversely, marginalised groups often face exclusion due to limited access to information. Public libraries act as essential mediating institutions capable of narrowing this knowledge gap by providing equal access to legal resources, civic education, and human rights information. When complemented with ICT-driven services, libraries can empower underserved communities—particularly in areas such as North-Central

Nigeria—by equipping them with the digital skills and knowledge needed for active involvement in legal processes and governance.

Complementing this perspective is Digital Inclusion Theory, which emphasises the importance of equitable access to digital tools and services in promoting civic empowerment and justice. Public libraries actively promote digital inclusion by helping community members use e-governance platforms, access online legal databases, and participate in virtual legal aid or dispute resolution services. Nonetheless, the theory also underscores ongoing challenges such as infrastructure deficiencies and low digital literacy levels, which can obstruct the full realisation of these opportunities. Enhancing the technological capacity of public libraries through ICT infrastructure, staff training, and user education can help overcome these barriers. In this way, libraries can play a crucial role in advancing Sustainable Development Goal 16 (SDG 16) by expanding access to justice, promoting public participation, and enhancing institutional accountability.

Additionally, Institutional Theory offers a perspective for understanding the role of public libraries within broader governance and judicial systems. Libraries are not isolated entities but part of a network of institutions that foster transparency, accountability, and participatory governance. External institutional factors, such as policy mandates, government funding, and administrative support, significantly influence their ability to promote legal knowledge and civic engagement. Strengthening the institutional integration of public libraries, especially in North-Central Nigeria, can enhance their contributions to peacebuilding, justice delivery, and democratic development. In this way, public libraries are recognised not just as service providers but as vital agents in fostering informed, active, and justice-oriented communities. The link between public libraries, ICT integration, and the realisation of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 16—focused on advancing justice, peace, and strong institutions—serves as the foundation for this study's conceptual framework. This section discusses the concept and scope of SDG 16, the role of public libraries in social development and governance, and the benefits and challenges of integrating information and communication technology (ICT) into library services.

Definition and Scope of SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions)

Public libraries play a vital role in advancing Sustainable Development Goal 16 (SDG 16) by promoting justice, peace, and strengthening institutions, especially in developing countries. Balôck (2020) noted that, despite financial constraints, libraries in Cameroon have actively contributed to democratic participation, social cohesion, and dispute resolution, key aspects of SDG 16. In Nigeria, Igbinovia (2016) emphasised that libraries are not only raising awareness of the SDGs but also helping achieve them by providing access to vital information and community resources. Incorporated into broader development plans, Popoola (2019) noted that libraries also support SDG 3 by enhancing health literacy through access to accurate and timely health information for both professionals and the public. This effort is significant in countries like Nigeria, where limited access to credible health information can significantly impact public health outcomes. According to Hope, Sr. (2020), while nations still face challenges in implementing SDG 16, progress in this area remains essential for the success of other goals. It is widely reported that libraries, by serving as accessible spaces for civic engagement, legal literacy, and the sharing of information, are uniquely positioned to bridge informational gaps and encourage dialogue on governance and human rights. Their ability to promote institutional trust and increase public awareness of justice-related issues makes them indispensable in communities dealing with sociopolitical instability and systemic inequality.

The Role of Public Libraries in Social Development and Governance

Public libraries play a vital role in building strong, democratic societies by providing equal access to information, encouraging lifelong learning, and supporting active civic participation. As Sipilä (2013) notes, libraries serve as inclusive spaces that empower individuals to participate meaningfully in public life through access to trustworthy and relevant information. Gorham et al. (2016) also emphasised that public libraries serve as catalysts for social justice and human rights by providing services that bridge digital gaps, offer social support, and address educational inequalities. This role also includes supplying legal information, government policies, and human rights resources, enabling citizens to stay informed about governance and legal processes. Discussing this ongoing process, both Sipilä (2013) and Gorham et al. (2016) argued that libraries improve transparency and civic awareness by equipping communities with knowledge about laws, social justice, and public policy. Through these efforts, libraries strengthen democratic institutions and enhance community resilience by giving individuals the tools they need to advocate for their rights and participate effectively in civic discussions.

ICT Integration in Public Libraries: Opportunities and Challenges

Integrating information and communication technology (ICT) into Nigerian public libraries is widely regarded as a crucial step towards achieving sustainable development and enhancing service delivery. Nwankwo et al. (2020) and Adebayo et al. (2018) argue that adopting ICT significantly improves library operations by strengthening staff skills, facilitating inter-library resource sharing, and broadening access to digital information. Aina et al. observed that ICT not only streamlines management practices but also enhances the user experience, making libraries more responsive to the evolving needs of their communities. Despite these advantages, effective implementation still encounters substantial challenges. Oghenetega et al. (2014) identified key barriers, including inadequate staff training, persistent underfunding, and weak technological infrastructure, which have hindered ICT development in several Nigerian states. Nonetheless, efforts to integrate digital tools into library services are ongoing, reflecting a growing awareness of ICT's transformative potential. As a solution, Nwankwo et al. (2020) and Adebayo et al. (2018) recommend focusing on capacity building, infrastructure development, and supportive policy frameworks. Addressing these systemic issues will enable libraries to more effectively contribute to Nigeria's sustainable development goals and ensure equitable access to information for all citizens.

Public Libraries and Access to Legal Information

Public libraries play a vital role in advancing social justice, human rights, and legal awareness. According to Gorham et al. (2016), libraries serve as information centres that offer free access to government regulations, human rights resources, and legal materials. By providing legal literacy programmes, seminars, and public discussions, libraries promote civic participation and foster transparency in governance. Additionally, Gorham et al. (2016) noted that libraries collaborate with civil society organisations and legal professionals to deliver training on social justice and conflict resolution. They also serve as important centres for human rights education, providing resources on fundamental freedoms and offering legal assistance. Furthermore, Jaeger et al. (2015) stated that libraries support digital inclusion by providing access to online legal databases and offering technology training, thereby helping individuals navigate the digital landscape effectively. Despite these initiatives, Gorham et al. (2016) noted that libraries often struggle to convey their importance to policymakers and donors. In many communities, they remain the only institutions capable of offering a wide range of social justice

and human rights services, emphasising their crucial role in cultivating an informed and empowered society.

ICT Facilities in Public Libraries for SDG 16 Implementation

Public libraries utilise information and communication technology (ICT) to enhance access to legal information and promote digital inclusion, both of which are essential for achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 16. According to Bertot (2016), libraries support economic, educational, health, and civic engagement by offering free access to ICT resources, broadband connectivity, and digital literacy training. These services empower individuals and communities, encouraging increased participation in social and economic activities. Balôck (2020) noted that libraries play a key role in advancing justice, peace, and strong institutions by serving as platforms for public discussions, conflict resolution, and the dissemination of information on national issues. Additionally, Alex-Nmecha and Igbinovia (2020) noted that libraries contribute to the SDGs by offering information literacy programmes that equip users with the skills to access, evaluate, and effectively utilise information. Despite challenges, Nwankwo et al. (2020) believe that the adoption of ICT in libraries enhances service delivery and supports sustainable development by integrating online dispute resolution mechanisms and e-governance platforms. By acting as intermediaries between the public and the government, libraries foster institutional trust and promote transparency and accountability in governance.

Public Libraries as Agents of Peacebuilding and Institutional Strengthening

According to Scott (2011), public libraries play a vital role in promoting justice, peace, and strong institutions, as outlined in Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). They serve as neutral spaces for dialogue, conflict resolution, and community building, encouraging inclusive discussions on social issues. By supporting knowledge sharing, civic participation, and social inclusion, libraries contribute to peacebuilding efforts and help bridge societal divides (Echezona, 2007; Scott, 2011). Despite financial challenges, Balôck (2020) observed that public libraries in Cameroon actively support SDG 16 by providing services that foster social cohesion, democracy, and conflict resolution. These initiatives demonstrate the ability of libraries to act as catalysts for peace, even in resource-limited environments. As information hubs, libraries can prevent conflicts, promote harmony, and enhance societal well-being. Scott (2011) and Balôck (2020) argue that libraries strengthen communities by offering access to vital resources, encouraging civic involvement, and supporting marginalised groups. By fostering inclusivity and equitable access to information, libraries play a crucial role in promoting the development of fairer and more peaceful societies.

Challenges and Barriers in Implementing ICT for Peace and Justice in Public Libraries

Limited Funding and Outdated Infrastructure

Public libraries in Nigeria often face financial limitations that hinder upgrading their ICT infrastructure, resulting in outdated computers, poor internet connectivity, and a shortage of modern digital tools. These conditions significantly limit libraries' ability to provide services that facilitate access to legal information, civic education, and justice-related resources (Okafor, 2020; Speirs, 2010).

Inadequate Access to Legal and E-Governance Platforms

Public libraries are limited in their capacity to support justice and transparency efforts due to the lack of dependable online legal databases and e-governance tools. According to Osuigwe

and Unagha (2011), this infrastructural deficit hinders citizens' access to vital information, making it more difficult for them to participate in democratic processes and protect their rights.

The Digital Divide and Low Literacy in ICT

Disparities in internet access and digital literacy in rural and underserved areas worsen the digital divide. Individuals with limited or no computer skills often struggle to access ICT-based library services. As noted by Oghenetega et al. (2014), this challenge disproportionately affects marginalised communities, obstructing the promotion of inclusive access to justice and peace-related information.

Weak Policy Frameworks and Institutional Marginalisation

Public libraries are often overlooked in national agendas for peace, justice, and digital development. This lack of policy focus results in low prioritisation and difficulties in securing funding. According to Speirs (2010), without explicit government support, libraries are frequently marginalised in national development strategies, which hampers their capacity to expand ICT services for peace and justice.

Insufficient Skilled Personnel and Poor Staff Conditions

Librarians often struggle with the technical skills required to operate and manage ICT tools for peace and governance initiatives. This problem is exacerbated by a lack of training opportunities and inadequate working conditions, which negatively impact motivation and performance. According to Okafor (2020), these human resource constraints impede the long-term success of ICT-based library programmes.

Inconsistent Government and NGO Engagement

Ongoing support from government agencies and non-government organisations is vital for expanding and maintaining ICT initiatives in public libraries. However, Osuigwe and Unagha (2011) emphasised that this support has been inconsistent or minimal, impeding long-term planning, strategic partnerships, and the overall effect of ICT on peace and justice services.

Methodology

For this study, a descriptive survey design was chosen to investigate the relationship between public library ICT use and the implementation of SDG 16 in North-Central Nigeria. Using structured questionnaires, this design supports data collection from a large population, enabling respondents to express their opinions openly. Descriptive surveys are well-suited for examining real-world phenomena without interference and are commonly employed to evaluate attitudes, behaviours, and institutional functions. This approach is suitable for assessing how public libraries disseminate information and utilise ICT to promote peace, justice, and strong institutions. Our study population comprises 194 librarians from six state library boards in North-Central Nigeria: Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, and Plateau. Due to the manageable population size, we used a total enumeration method to include all librarians as participants. To ensure fairness, we employed a random sampling technique. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire with five sections: demographic information, the importance of SDG 16, the role of public libraries in information dissemination, ICT utilisation for peace and justice, and libraries' support for implementing SDG 16. The data were analysed with descriptive statistics, including frequency tables, percentages, and means, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) was applied.

Table 1: Population of Study

S/N	Public Libraries	Librarians
1	Benue State Library Board	27
2	Kogi State Library Board	33
3	Kwara State Library Board	36
4	Nasarawa State Library Board	29
5	Niger State Library Board	31
6	Plateau State Library Board	38
	Total	194

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2023

Discussion of Findings

Table 2: Influence of ICT Facilities Utilised for the Implementation of Peace and Justice Goal

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	N	FX	\bar{x}	STD	Decision
		4	3	2	1	173				
1	Public libraries, through the use of ICT facilities, facilitate public awareness and the effective dissemination of information about the peace and justice goals	96	57	16	4	173	591	3.42	0.92	Agreed
2	Public libraries through the use of ICT facilities ensure and enable efficient resource usage for the attainment of peace and justice	97	49	21	6	173	583	3.37	0.87	Agreed
3	ICT facilities ensure faster upgrading in the quality of services provided by public libraries about peace and justice	72	47	33	21	173	516	2.98	0.48	Agreed
4	The use of Internet enables the provision of current and useful information necessary for the achievement of peace and justice in the society	105	40	21	7	173	589	3.40	0.90	Agreed
5	The use of ICT facilities, such as computers enables information generation, processing, storage and information dissemination about peace and justice	89	49	19	16	173	557	3.22	0.72	Agreed
6	Libraries through ICT ensure public access to information and protect fundamental human freedoms	65	49	32	27	173	498	2.88	0.38	Agreed

7	Libraries through the use of ICT create an enabling environment where information on peace and justice can be accessed and use by the general public	89	47	24	13	173	558	3.23	0.72	Agreed
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Key: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), Strongly Disagreed (SD)

The data presented in Table 2 show that seven items were listed for librarians regarding the influence of ICT facilities used to implement the peace and justice goal. All seven items received high mean scores, all above the benchmark of 2.5. These items include: item 1, which states that public libraries using ICT facilities facilitate public awareness and effective dissemination of information about the peace and justice goal ($\bar{x}=3.42$; $SD=0.92$); item 4, which indicates that the use of the Internet enables the provision of current and useful information necessary for achieving peace and justice in society ($\bar{x}=3.40$; $SD=0.90$); item 2, which notes that public libraries using ICT facilities ensure and enable efficient resource usage for the attainment of peace and justice ($\bar{x}=3.37$; $SD=0.87$); item 7, which states that libraries using ICT create an environment where information on peace and justice can be accessed and used by the public ($\bar{x}=3.23$; $SD=0.72$); item 5, which points out that the use of ICT facilities like computers enables information generation, processing, storage, and dissemination about peace and justice ($\bar{x}=3.22$; $SD=0.72$); item 3, which explains that ICT facilities ensure faster upgrading of the quality of services provided by public libraries on peace and justice ($\bar{x}=2.98$; $SD=0.48$); and item 6, which mentions that libraries using ICT ensure public access to information and protect fundamental human freedoms ($\bar{x}=2.88$; $SD=0.38$). Overall, the highest mean score was observed in item 1, regarding public libraries using ICT to facilitate public awareness and the effective dissemination of information about peace and justice goals. The analysis indicates that items 4, 2, 7, and 5 received strong agreement from respondents, while items 3 and 6 were also agreed upon.

Table 3: Roles of Public Libraries in Supporting the Implementation of the Peace and Justice Goal

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	N	FX	\bar{x}	STD	Decision
		4	3	2	1	173				
1	Public libraries promote Open Access Initiatives through specialised information gathering by librarians on the goal of peace and justice which make scholarly publications on peace and justice available to the general public	82	43	29	16	173	531	3.07	0.57	Agreed
2	Improving the literacy of citizens by pooling together relevant resources to support education and training targeted at formal or informal sectors	82	72	8	11	173	571	3.30	0.80	Agreed

3	Formal and informal training by collaborating with NGOs and other public sectors in meeting the local needs of the inhabitants of a particular area	88	47	21	17	173	552	3.19	0.69	Agreed
4	Introducing advocacy programmes through seminars, conferences, road walks, social media technology, and others like television and radio interviews to sensitize public members of the libraries' collections on peace and justice	65	49	32	27	173	498	2.88	0.38	Agreed
5	Formulating policies through librarian bodies like NLA and LRCN that will articulate each aspect of peace and justice	57	67	34	15	173	512	2.96	0.46	Agreed
6	Through an evaluation by assessing and analysing the progress of the peace and justice goal programme promoted by the library	85	43	29	16	173	543	3.14	0.64	Agreed

Key: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), Strongly Disagreed (SD)

Table 3 shows that six items were listed for librarians to respond to regarding the roles of public libraries in supporting the implementation of the peace and justice goal in North-central Nigeria. All six items received high mean scores, all above the average benchmark of 2.50. These items include: item 2, which involves improving citizens' literacy by gathering relevant resources to support education and training targeted at both formal and informal sectors (\bar{x} =3.30; SD=0.80); item 3, related to providing formal and informal training by collaborating with NGOs and other public sectors to meet the local needs of the community (\bar{x} =3.19; SD=0.69); item 6, involving evaluating and analysing the progress of the peace and justice goal program promoted by the library (\bar{x} =3.14; SD=0.64); item 1, where public libraries promote Open Access Initiatives by gathering specialized information on peace and justice, making scholarly publications accessible to the public (\bar{x} =2.96; SD=0.46); and item 4, which emphasizes introducing advocacy programs through seminars, conferences, walk-a-thons, social media, and media interviews to raise awareness of the libraries' collections related to peace and justice (\bar{x} =2.88; SD=0.38).

The study demonstrated that ICT facilities in public libraries play a vital role in increasing public awareness and effectively disseminating information about peace and justice. According to

Nwabueze and Ozioko (2016), ICT improves resource utilisation, enhances service quality, and ensures that relevant and up-to-date information necessary for societal peace and justice is easily accessible. ICT also assists in creating, processing, storing, and sharing information, while providing an easy platform for public participation. Public libraries equipped with ICT significantly contribute to social and economic development by offering the public access to information and safeguarding fundamental human rights. These findings highlight the broader importance of ICT in achieving Nigeria's sustainable development goals.

Furthermore, the study emphasised the diverse roles that public libraries play in supporting SDG 16. One key role is promoting Open Access Initiatives by organising and sharing scholarly publications on peace and justice. According to Anyaoku (2016), libraries also improve literacy through educational resources and partnerships with NGOs for training programmes. Additionally, libraries actively engage in advocacy through seminars, conferences, and media outreach to raise awareness about peace and justice issues. Onah et al. (2015) noted that libraries contribute to policy development by assessing and analysing peace-related programmes, often working with professional organisations such as the Nigerian Library Association (NLA) and the Librarians' Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN). These findings reaffirm that public libraries serve as essential institutions in providing ICT access and information, aligning with global efforts supported by organisations like the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA). By integrating ICT into their services, libraries not only close information gaps but also enhance their role in peacebuilding and justice advocacy, further emphasising their importance in achieving sustainable development goals.

Conclusion

The study concludes that public libraries play a vital role in promoting justice, peace, and strong institutions, as outlined in SDG 16, by effectively utilizing ICT resources. According to Nwabueze and Ozioko (2016), ICT enhances public awareness, facilitates knowledge sharing, and improves service delivery, making libraries powerful tools for driving social change. By leveraging digital resources, public libraries ensure access to relevant and current information, fostering an environment that supports civic participation and the protection of fundamental human rights. Additionally, public libraries contribute to peacebuilding by supporting literacy initiatives, promoting Open Access Initiatives, and collaborating with stakeholders to provide both formal and informal education on justice and governance. Anyaoku (2016) emphasised that libraries play a crucial role in advocacy and policymaking, ensuring the successful implementation of programs related to justice and peace. However, to maximise their impact, challenges such as insufficient funding, limited infrastructure, and policy gaps must be addressed. To improve the effectiveness of public libraries in achieving SDG 16, it is important to strengthen institutional support, invest in ICT infrastructure, and develop policies that empower libraries as centres for social development and information access. Onah et al. (2015) stated that addressing these barriers would enable public libraries in North-Central Nigeria to reach their full potential as catalysts for sustainable justice and peace, contributing significantly to both national and global development goals.

Recommendations

Enhancing ICT Infrastructure for Better Civic Education and Legal Access: Increasing funding for digital infrastructure is essential to maximise the use of ICT resources in public libraries to achieve SDG 16. To provide librarians and users with access to up-to-date ICT technologies, reliable internet, and digital literacy training, government agencies, private sector partners, and NGOs should collaborate. This partnership would enhance the public's access to civic

education and legal information, enabling people to participate more effectively in governance, human rights, and justice-related matters. Furthermore, integrating e-governance systems into library services will strengthen their role in digital civic engagement.

Strengthening public libraries as hubs for peacebuilding and institutional development: By implementing targeted programs such as conflict resolution seminars, legal literacy campaigns, and community involvement projects, public libraries can further enhance their role in promoting peace, justice, and institutional growth. Libraries can support citizens in learning their rights and encourage discussions on justice-related topics by forming partnerships with law enforcement, civil society organisations, and legal institutions. To ensure the sustainability and broader societal impact of library services, authorities should also recognise libraries as vital institutions for peacebuilding by integrating them into national development plans.

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